

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 4 | OCTOBER - DECEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue IV | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“FIRST AND TENTH FOREVER”

I was ten when you left Calinan
You never witnessed my teen and adult years
Even in times of our grief
When we lost our parents

God really works mysteriously through FB
He connects me to an advocate of differently abled people
A simple clicked like for all his posts, he noticed me
Then asked me if I know of a DAP, my look alike
Grateful of tenth of October 2020.

I have no idea of who really you are
All I know you are first, I am tenth
Then I met your family but without you in Dumaguete
I am impressed by the fine manners of your kids

For 25 years with no communication
We can finally enjoy the chance of asking many questions
Where have you been Manong?
Why have you disappeared?

A family video call has been set 10th of January 2021
We are so touched of your sorry from Pampanga
For all your failures and troubles affecting our family
Silence, tears, and laughter begin, we reunite on line

First of May 2021 has broken our hearts
Pandemic has taken your life away from us
How sad is your fate, no more physical reunion
One thing for sure - you are first and I am tenth forever

Categories

Please **HIGHLIGHT** the category for your submission:

- ◆ Poetry
- ◆ Short Stories
- ◆ Essays
- ◆ Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- ◆ Creative Corner
- ◆ Others: _____ (Please specify)

After you fill this out, kindly send it to our official email at **binasbookers2013@gmail.com**. Make sure that your work is final before you send it, as any revisions will no longer be accommodated once the process starts. The entire publication will be posted on our official site once it is finalized, at this link:

<https://sites.google.com/view/binasbookers2013/home>.

The online publication process typically takes **7 to 10 days**. However, if you opt for a publication that includes **peer review**, the timeline may vary depending on the availability of reviewers. We appreciate your patience and understanding in this matter.

If you want a hand-signed certificate, we can provide you with a copy. However, you will be responsible for the shipping fee: **₱450 for Luzon, ₱300 for Visayas, and ₱450 for Mindanao**.

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